

Development of Microsoft Access for using in Library

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Abstract

The object of research in the preparation of this paper is the Microsoft Access 2010 database application system which is a combination of several previous tasks that have been made in the form of a Microsoft Access-based database application design. Microsoft Access could be applied on Library for arrange, search, and documented visitor, donation of book and list of book data.

Keywords: *Microsoft access, Library, and Book data.*

Introduction

Microsoft Access application is an application used to manage databases. This application has several advantages compared to other database applications, such as in terms of ease of operation and availability of applications to the public. Database is a collection of data that is managed based on certain interrelated provisions making it easier to manage. Database is also a collection of data or information stored systematically. The database contained in Microsoft Access can be developed into a separate application according to the desired model and function. Even in its development, it is simple, it is enough to create a table, then connect it through a relationship, make queries, forms and reports.

According to the Library Law in Chapter I, article 1, it is stated that the library is an institution that collects printed and recorded knowledge, manages it in a special way to meet the intellectual needs of its users through various ways of knowledge interaction. In a traditional sense, a library is a collection of books and magazines. Although it can be interpreted as an individual's private collection, the library is more commonly known as a large collection that is financed and operated by a city or institution, and is used by people who on average cannot afford to buy many books at their own expense.

Data type is used to determine the data type of a field in a table, with the following type options:

1. Text, To receive text data up to 255 characters consisting of letters, numbers and graphic symbols.
2. Memo, To receive text data up to 65,535 characters consisting of letters, numbers, punctuation marks and graphic symbols. This data type cannot be used as a reference for sorting data (index).

3. Number, To accept digits, minus sign and decimal point. The number data type has 5 choices of number size and a certain number of digits.
4. Date/Time, To receive date and time data, as well as the year value starting from year 100 to year 9999
5. Currency, To receive digit data, minus sign, and decimal point sign with a precision level of 15 decimal digits to the left of the decimal point and 4 digits to the right of the decimal point.
6. AutoNumber, To display the automatic serial number, which is in the form of numeric data starting from 1 with a difference of 1.
7. Yes/No. This type is used to receive data from two values, namely Yes/no, true/False or On/Off.
8. OLE Object, To receive data in the form of graphic objects, spreadsheets, digital photos, sound recordings or videos that can be retrieved from other application programs. The maximum size is 1 gigabyte.
9. Hyperlink, To receive data in the form of colored and underlined text and graphics and this data type is related to the network.
10. Attachment, To receive data in the form of image files, spreadsheets, documents, graphics and other file types.
11. Lookup Wizard, To display one of several types of data in a list. You can retrieve the data from existing tables or queries.

Encrypting the database serves to make the data in Microsoft Access unreadable by unauthorized persons, by setting a password, so that only people who know the password can

enter to access Microsoft Access. Start up serves to limit the display of database application settings in Microsoft Access so only interested people can access the settings in the database that have been set by start up. Things that can be limited to start-up settings start from the display, settings, use of the default menu.

Based on the arguments listed previously, the author will present a report on the development applications from the database that have been created while studying Business Application Computers.

Material and Method

The object of research in the preparation of this paper is the Microsoft Access 2010 database application system which is a combination of several previous tasks that have been made in the form of a Microsoft Access-based database application design. The data collection techniques that I use to write this paper are as follows:

1. Journal Reference

In compiling this paper, I collected references from several journals on the internet, so that it would be easier for me to write this paper.

2. Youtube Visual Reference

In YouTube there is already a discussion about the process of creating a database on Access so that I can follow the tutorial shown on YouTube.

Result and Discussion

When a visitor enters the FEBI library, there is no need to fill in visitor data through the manual, just fill it in through the visitor data form and save it directly to the visitor data report.

FORM DATA PENGUNJUNG

NIM [Dropdown]

JENIS KELAKSANAAN

JENJANG

JANIS PESERTA DIDIK

KODING PENYUSUNAN

KODING MATA PELAJARAN

KEMENTERIAN

TANGGAL KEBERUKUAN

SIMPAN TAMBAH FORM HAPUS KELUAR

Clear Form

This form serves to enter data regarding borrowing and returning books in the library and is directly connected to the borrowing and returning data report. In this form we also create a search field so that the library can more easily find the data that has been previously entered into this form.

FORM DATA PEMINJAMAN DAN PENGEMBALIAN

NIM [Dropdown]

JANIS

JENIS LEMBAR

NAMA PUSTAKA

JENJANG

NAMA PENGEMBAL

JANIS PENGEMBAL

JENJANG

JANIS PENGEMBALAN

KEMENTERIAN

KODING PENYUSUNAN

KODING MATA PELAJARAN

KEMENTERIAN

TANGGAL KEMBALIAN

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